

APPENDIX E

Iteration 1 results

1 Usability

Table E.1
Summary of Usability Evaluation

	Item	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Comments
1	It is easy to learn how to use the application.	Yes	Yes	Yes	2: Tutorial must have an option to return 3: The instructions read at the beginning are useful
2	It is easy to use the application.	Yes	Yes	Yes	2: It is important that when you have to select the atom/star, the message is below the circles and people are paying attention to the chat, it is better to put the message in a way that looks better. 3: I had to stop to think how to start at the beginning.
3	Steps to use the application are easy to follow.	Yes	Yes	Yes	
4	Labels and texts on buttons are clear and concise.	Yes	No	Yes	1: It may be strange that there is "Send" and "Send response", that may confuse. 2: They should only change the word "constellation" to "stars"
5	Conserve overall consistency and behavior with the mobile platform.	Yes	No	Yes	2: The same message of point 2
6	Minimalist design - Excessive features are removed.	Yes	Yes	Yes	2: black background can be analyzed if it can be a little more concise with the rest of the interface 3: here was nothing left over, although at the beginning the chat seemed to me that I could write
7	Content is concise and clear.	Yes	Yes	Yes	
8	Provide feedback to the user about the state of the system.	Yes	No	Yes	3: It is very good to know what my teammates are doing
9	Number of buttons/links are reasonable.	Yes	Yes	Yes	
10	Elements of the interface provide visual feedback when are pressed.	Yes	Yes	Yes	
11	Ensures that not any message/feedback is being covered by the user's hand or finger.	Yes	No	Yes	
12	Colors used provide a good contrast.	Yes	Yes	Yes	2: Same as point 6 3: I found it hard to see that my atom was selected, I think that white does not contrast
13	Colors used provide good readability.	Yes	Yes	Yes	
14	Icons are clear to understand - there is no ambiguity.	Yes	Yes	Yes	
15	Font size and spacing ensure good readability.	Yes	No	No	2: The font size of the chat may be a little larger and could support color blindness
16	Speak the language of the users (not technical)	Yes	Yes	Yes	
17	It helps users recognize, diagnose and recover errors.	Yes	No	Yes	
18	Error messages are free of technical language	Yes	Yes	Yes	
19	Error messages clearly explain how to solve the problem.	Yes	Yes	Yes	
20	Help messages are clear and unambiguous.	Yes	Yes	Yes	

	Item	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Comments
21	Instructions are easily visible or easily recoverable when appropriate.	Yes	No	No	2: Same as point 2
22	By making mistakes, mistakes can be easily corrected.	No	Yes	Yes	1: Once you make a mistake there is no going back, but I think it is part of the design of the activity so it is good that it is so.
23	By making a mistake, external help is required to continue using the application.	No	No	Yes	2: It could be allowed to send a message after a time if the student does not answer, to help him/her if he/she does not know what to do
24	Images (stars and/or atoms) allow to identify their number and associated color.	Yes	Yes	Yes	
25	The tutorial is clear and allows you to understand the dynamics of the game.	Yes	Yes	Yes	2: Tutorial must have an option to return, in case it is not clear

2 Validity and reliability

Figure E.1: Parallel analysis scree plot form A

Table E.2

Communalities Form A

Item	h2	u2									
1	0,071	0,929	8	0,224	0,776	15	0,26	0,74	22	0,34	0,66
2	0,413	0,587	9	0,268	0,732	16	0,657	0,343	23	0,957	0,043
3	0,467	0,533	10	0,22	0,78	17	0,695	0,305	24	0,334	0,666
4	0,548	0,452	11	0,851	0,149	18	0,402	0,598	25	0,848	0,152
5	0,631	0,369	12	0,894	0,106	19	0,222	0,778			
6	0,107	0,893	13	0,404	0,596	20	0,782	0,218			

Table E.3
Exploratory Factor Analysis Form A

Item	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Assessment Criteria	Cronbach's Alpha	Variance %
7	.31							Mention actions/plans to solve the problem.	0.718	.4600
16	.72							Mention actions to be taken together to solve the problem.		
17	.75							Mention actions to be carried out by the other members of his/her group (control).		
19		.45						Evaluate the success of the strategy to solve the problem.	0.749	
20		.85						He/She proposes changes in the actions to reach the solution.		
24		.48						Evaluate the success of the partners' actions to solve the problem.		
25		.87						He/She proposes changes in the actions of his/her partners if the group can not reach a solution.		
12			.90					Identify errors in the understanding of the problem by the group.	0.951	
14			.93					Mention ideas to solve errors in understanding the problem.		
6				.12				Ask about others' ideas about the purpose of the problem.	0.554	
8				.24				Ask about actions/plans of other group members to solve the problem.		
10				.37				Ask about what is necessary to solve the problem.		
18				.41				Mention the strategy (actions) to solve the problem.		
22				.42				Mention roles to be taken by him/her and his/her teammates.		
23				.91				Mention actions to be carried out by the other members of his/her group (control) according to the assigned role.		
3					.64			Mention what he/she understand of the problem to be solved.	0.671	
5					.78			Mention his/her ideas about the purpose of the problem		
9					.42			Mention what is necessary to solve the problem.		
11						.98		Identify gaps (lack of information) in the understanding of the problem by his/her group.	0.713	
13						.55		Mention ideas to resolve gaps (lack of information) in understanding the problem.		
1							.26	Mention his/her ideas/opinions when necessary.	0.567	
2							.33	Ask about the ideas/opinions of other group members.		
4							.30	Ask about what others understand about the problem to be solved.		
15							.23	Ask about joint actions to be taken to solve the problem.		
21							.20	Ask his/her teammates about the roles they must take to solve the problem.		

Note: Rotated factors matrix, method of analysis of principal factors with varimax rotation.

Figure E.2: Parallel analysis scree plot form B

Table E.4

Communalities Form A

Item	h2	u2	Item	h2	u2	Item	h2	u2	Item	h2	u2
1	0,062	0,938	8	0,309	0,691	16	0,454	0,546	23	0,934	0,066
2	0,444	0,556	9	0,167	0,833	17	0,541	0,459	24	0,512	0,488
3	0,245	0,755	10	0,287	0,713	18	0,252	0,748	25	0,648	0,352
4	0,435	0,565	11	0,504	0,496	19	0,435	0,565			
5	0,706	0,294	12	0,144	0,856	20	0,557	0,443			
6	0,855	0,145	13	0,296	0,704	21	0,048	0,952			
7	0,466	0,534	15	0,323	0,677	22	0,539	0,461			

Table E.5

Exploratory Factor Analysis Form B

Item	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Assessment Criteria	Cronbach's Alpha	Variance %
2	.60								Ask about the ideas/opinions of other group members.	0.617	.4234
4	.64								Ask about what others understand about the problem to be solved.		
8	.45								Ask about actions/plans of other group members to solve the problem.		
15	.50								Ask about joint actions to be taken to solve the problem.		
22		.71							Mention roles to be taken by him/her and his/her teammates.	0.823	

23	.95		Mention actions to be carried out by the other members of his/her group (control) according to the assigned role.	
12	.34		Identify errors in the understanding of the problem by the group.	0.561
25	.72		He/She proposes changes in the actions of his/her partners if the group can not reach a solution.	
20	.72		He/She proposes changes in the actions to reach the solution.	
6	.92		Ask about others' ideas about the purpose of the problem.	0.53
10	.48		Ask about what is necessary to solve the problem.	
19	.64		Evaluate the success of the strategy to solve the problem.	0.641
24	.70		Evaluate the success of the partners' actions to solve the problem.	
1		.22	Mention his/her ideas/opinions when necessary.	0.646
7		.46	Mention actions/plans to solve the problem.	
16		.52	Mention actions to be taken together to solve the problem.	
17		.57	Mention actions to be carried out by the other members of his/her group (control).	
18		.26	Mention the strategy (actions) to solve the problem.	
21		.19	Ask his/her teammates about the roles they must take to solve the problem.	
3		.36	Mention what he/she understand of the problem to be solved.	0.412
5		.83	Mention his/her ideas about the purpose of the problem	
9		.35	Mention what is necessary to solve the problem.	
11		.70	Identify gaps (lack of information) in the understanding of the problem by his/her group.	0.563
13		.53	Mention ideas to resolve gaps (lack of information) in understanding the problem.	

Note: Rotated factors matrix, method of analysis of principal factors with varimax rotation.